

Conference Report

Second International Congress on Chocolate and Cocoa in Medicine Held in Barcelona, Spain, 25–26th September 2015

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† On behalf of the International Society of Chocolate and Cocoa in Medicine.

1. Preface

Cocoa powder is a product derived from the beans of the *Theobroma cacao* tree, which is considered a good source of fiber (26%–40%), proteins (15%–20%), carbohydrates (about 15%) and lipids (10%–24%; generally, 10%–12%). It also contains minerals, vitamins and some bioactive compounds such as flavonoids, fiber, and methylxanthines, as is the case of theobromine. In recent years, cocoa and its derivatives such as chocolate have been the focus of increasing interest, mainly because of their high content of flavonoids, which are compounds with antioxidant activity. Cocoa contains flavanols such as (–)-epicatechin and catechin as monomers, and dimers or larger polymers derived from both of these, known as procyanidins. Due to this particular composition, and mainly based on its activity as an antioxidant, as well as through other mechanisms, cocoa consumption has been reported to promote beneficial effects on cardiovascular health, metabolism, brain and immune functions, and in cancer prevention, among others.

In order to further our understanding of, and disseminate the latest findings on the healthy properties of cocoa and chocolate, the International Society of Chocolate and Cocoa in Medicine (ISCHOM) was founded in 2010 in Florence (<http://ischom.com/ischom/>). This Society aims to gather information and become a forum of discussion and debate on cocoa and chocolate, not only among researchers from around the world, but also to introduce the science involved and the latest findings to the public. Cultural and educational promotion of the benefits of cocoa and chocolate on human health is another of the Society's major concerns. Finally, ISCHOM provides information on developing healthy habits regarding the inclusion of cocoa and chocolate in our diet.

In this context, after the first congress in Florence in 2014, ISCHOM held its second meeting in Barcelona, Spain, on 25 and 26 September 2015 (<https://www.eiseverywhere.com/ehome/117409/263536/>). By means of these annual meetings, the Society pursues the constant sharing and updating of current knowledge concerning the health properties of cocoa and chocolate. The event not only brings together international researchers, but also diverse companies in order to strengthen the knowledge in this field. About 90 delegates from 12 different countries attended the Society's second congress. It was organized into five scientific sessions with two lectures each.

The sessions that took place in Barcelona were focused on different topics in order to shed some light on a wide range of valuable effects of chocolate and cocoa on our health. Some of the issues discussed were the role of chocolate and cocoa as cardioprotective agents and its health claims, their effects on metabolism and their own metabolism; the possible role of cocoa as a preventive

Results: Significant correlations between the C-FFQ and the EFSA-Q/24HDR for the most common cocoa and chocolate products were observed. A large variety of cocoa/chocolate products frequently consumed by the participants were detected by the C-FFQ and 24HDR, whereas they were not included in the EFSA-Q. When considering percentile classification, the majority of the individuals were classified in the same/adjacent quintile for the C-FFQ and the EFSA-Q or 24HDR.

Conclusion: In conclusion, the developed 90-item FFQ can be considered as a valid option for assessing the consumption frequency of cocoa- and chocolate-derived products. As far as we know, this is the most extensive questionnaire developed in relation to a wide range of several products containing chocolate in a traditional European diet. The use of this FFQ will allow individuals to be reasonably classified according to their cocoa consumption and therefore an evaluation of the impact of such intake on health and lifestyle in further studies.

3.11. Cocoa Intake Alleviates Hepatic Oxidative Stress in Zucker Diabetic Fatty Rats

Cordero-Herrera, I.; Martín, M.A.; Goya, L.; Ramos, S. *

Background and objectives: Chronic hyperglycemia in diabetes is associated with oxidative stress-mediated tissue damage. Cocoa and dark chocolate have demonstrated the ability to improve insulin sensitivity and modulate oxidative stress markers in diabetic patients. The present study is aimed at exploring the role of a cocoa-enriched diet in ameliorating the oxidative stress-induced damage in the liver of type 2 diabetic Zucker diabetic fatty (ZDF) rats.

Methodology: Male ZDF rats were fed a control or cocoa-rich diet (10%), and Zucker lean (ZL) animals received the control diet. Hepatic reactive oxygen species (ROS), carbonyl and glutathione (GSH) levels, as well as superoxide dismutase (SOD), heme oxygenase (HO-1), glutathione-S-transferase (GST), glutathione peroxidase (GPx), glutathione reductase (GR) and catalase (CAT) activities, and nuclear factor erythroid-derived 2-like 2 (Nrf2), as well as p65-nuclear factor-kappaB (NF-κB) expression were evaluated.

Results: Cocoa diet reduced ROS levels and carbonyl content in the liver of ZDF animals. The diminished activity of SOD and the enhanced activity of HO-1 in ZDF-C were returned to ZL values upon cocoa administration. Cocoa did not restore the decreased GST activity in either ZDF groups in comparison to ZL rats. GSH content and activities of GPx, GR and CAT remained unaltered among all animal groups. Moreover, the cocoa-rich diet suppressed total and phosphorylated Nrf2, as well as p65-NF-κB-enhanced levels observed in ZDF rats.

Conclusion: Cocoa protects the hepatocytes by improving the antioxidant competence in the liver of young type 2 diabetic ZDF rats.

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3.12. Gut Microbiota and Mucosal Immunity Are Influenced by Cocoa theobromine

Martín-Peláez, S. *; Rigo-Adrover, M.; Camps-Bossacoma, M.; Massot-Cladera, M.; Saldaña-Ruiz, S.; Franch, A.; Pérez-Cano, F.J.; Castell, M.

Background and objectives: Ingestion of cocoa has been shown to influence the immune system. The role of the bioactive components of cocoa (*i.e.*, flavonoids, fiber, theobromine) is not completely understood. The objective of this study was to evaluate the effect of cocoa theobromine on the intestinal compartment.

Methodology: Twenty-one three-week-old Lewis rats, were randomly assigned to three dietary groups ($n = 7$ per group) for 15 days: the reference group (RF), which was fed with a standard diet; the cocoa group (CC), which was fed with a standard diet containing 10% of a conventional cocoa powder; and the theobromine group (TB), which was fed with a standard diet including 0.25% theobromine (the same amount of theobromine as the CC diet). Fecal samples were obtained

at day 15 in order to establish bacterial populations, short chain fatty acids (SCFA), pH and IgA coating bacteria.

Results: The TB diet significantly inhibited the growth of the bacterial groups covered by *E. coli*, *Bif164*, *Strept* and *Chis150* probes compared to RF. This inhibitory effect was not observed when theobromine was ingested with cocoa (CC diet), except for *E. coli*. Both CC and TB diets increased the fecal amounts of total SCFA, but led to different percentages of the individual SCFA analyzed, except for butyric acid, which increased with both diets. The TB increased percentages of formic acid, whereas the CC diet increased the percentage of acetic acid. Only the TB diet led to changes in fecal pH, which was found to be significantly higher than the RF and CC diets. The TB and in particular the CC diets significantly decreased the percentages of fecal IgA-coating bacteria compared to the RF diet.

Conclusions: Theobromine present in cocoa has an important role in rat's intestinal gut microbiota and immune system modulation.

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3.13. Nutrimetabolomic Approach to Identify Biomarkers for Cocoa-Food Products Consumption Monitoring in Healthy Volunteers

Llorach, R. *; Farran-Codina, A.; Soriano, A.; Termes-Escalé, M.; Luna, O.; Martinez, C.; Bosch, N.; Garrido, P.; Llobet, J.M.; Andres-Lacueva, C.; Urpi-Sarda, M.

Background and objectives: Cocoa consumption has been related with some health-promoting activities mainly related to cardiovascular disease. Nutrimetabolomics explore the complex relationship between the consumption of dietary compounds and the maintenance of health or disease development with the aim of discovering new biomarkers of intake and effect. In this regard, the aim of this work was to study the urinary cocoa products' fingerprint in order to establish a definition for the future for a specific biomarker imprinting of cocoa in healthy and young volunteers.

Methodology: Cocoa-food product intake was defined according to an FFQ that had been previously completed by free-living, healthy volunteers. Subjects were stratified as higher consumer (≥ 5 g/day), medium (between 1.16 and 4.28 g/day) and lower consumer (≤ 1 g/day). Urine samples of subjects were analyzed using HPLC-Q-TOF-MS, followed by multivariate data analysis (orthogonal signal correction for partial least squares-based classification/discrimination model or OSC-PLSDA and hierarchical cluster analysis or HCA). The metabolomics analysis was carried out using R package MAIT, which includes an in-house food metabolome database.

Results and conclusions: Urinary metabolome showed significant differences between the three consumer groups. Several metabolites were associated with the consumption of cocoa-foods, the most important being those coming from theobromine metabolism. In addition, microbial polyphenol metabolites and vanillin-derived metabolites have also been putatively identified. These metabolites have been previously associated with cocoa intake in other populations; however, as far we know, this is one of the first time that these metabolites have been identified in a free-living, healthy and young population using a metabolomics approach. The study reinforces the interest in the replication of results as well as the capacity of metabolomics to identify cocoa-foods products' footprint, combining epidemiological nutritional data and metabolomics.

3.14. Intestinal Evaluation of Cocoa Diet as an Antiallergic Compound in Food Allergic Rats

Abril-Gil, M. *; Pérez-Cano, F.J.; Saldaña-Ruiz, S.; Franch, A.; Castell, M.

Background and Objectives: Food allergy (FA) is a chronic disease that is mainly mediated by IgE against food allergen (Fox, M., *et al. Eur. J. Public Health* 2013, 23, 757–762). Previous studies have demonstrated that a diet containing cocoa can attenuate the synthesis of IgE in a rat allergy model (Abril-Gil, M., *et al. Pharmacol Res* 2012, 65, 603–608). The aim of the present study was to study in